

Affine Control Systems on Non-Compact Lie Group

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we deal with affine control systems on a non-compact Lie group $cx+e$ group. First we study topological properties of the state space $Ef(1)$ and the automorphism orbit of $Ef(1)$. Affine control system, non-compact Lie group state space $Ef(1)$. Affine control systems on the generalized Heisenberg Lie groups are studied. Affine algebra, automorphism.

Keyword: Affine algebra, automorphism non-compact Lie group, state space $Ef(1)$, automorphism orbit of $Ef(1)$, affine control system.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper affine control systems on some specific lie group is called $cx+e$ group by relating to associated bilinear parts.

Related to the affine control system on lie groups, in $Ef(1)$. The authors Ayala and San Martin have the sub algebra of the Lie algebra $Ef(G)$ generated by the vector fields of a linear control system the drift vector field X is an infinitesimal automorphism i.e., $(X_K)_{K \in M}$ is a one-parameter subgroup of $Aut(G)$; have lifted the system itself to a right-invariant control system on Lie group $Ef(1)$ for compact connected and non-compact semi-simple Lie group.

The affine control systems on a non-compact Lie group $cx+e$ group have been investigated and given characterization.

1. Affine Control Systems on Lie Groups

If G is a connected Lie group with Lie algebra $L(G)$, the affine group $Ef(G)$ of G is the semi-direct product of $Aut(G)$ with G itself i.e., $Ef(G) = Aut(G) \times G$. The group operation of $Ef(G)$.

The identity element of $Aut(G)$ and e denotes the neutral element of G , then the group identity of $Ef(G)$ is $(1, a)$ and $(\Phi^{-1}, \Phi^{-1}(h^{-1}))$ In the invers of $(\Phi, h) \in Ef(G)$. Hence, $h \rightarrow (1, h)$ and $\Phi \rightarrow (\Phi, a)$ embed G into $Ef(G)$ and $Aut(G)$ into $Af(G)$ respectively. Therefore, G and $Aut(G)$ are subgroups of $Ef(G)$. The natural transitive action

$$Ef(G) \times G \rightarrow G$$

$$(\Phi, h_1).h_2 \rightarrow h_1\Phi(h_2)$$

Where $(\Phi, h_1) \in Ef(G)$ and $h_2 \in G$.

“Affine in the control” is used to describe class system.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = n(x) + h(x) v \text{ is considered affine control.}$$

Theorem: 1

Let $\Sigma = (Ef(1), D)$ be an affine control system. Then, the state space $Ef(1)$ is a locally compact Hausdorff space.

Proof:

$Ef(1)$ is a Hausdorff space is a lie group. The compactness for a given $x \in Ef(1)$ and neighborhood Z of x , the existence of some neighborhood Z of x such that. The topology on $Ef(1)$ half plane is homomorphic to the standard topology of M^2 .

Therefore, $\forall x \in Ef(1)$, the neighborhood Z of x is homeomorphic to an open ball. For each neighborhood Z of x , there is neighborhood W of x such $x \in W$. Since W is also homeomorphic to an open ball the closure of U is a closed ball.

Theorem: 2

The automorphism orbit of the state space $Ef(1)$ is dense.

Proof:

The set

$$J = \exp (cf(1) - [cf(1), cf(1)])$$

$Aut(Ef(1))$ -orbit of $Ef(1)$. The exponential mapping from the tangent plane to the surface of diffeomorphism. Then two elements $h_1, h_2 \in J$ the line segment $h_1 h_2$ which is parallel to $[Ef(1), Ef(1)]$,

$$\Phi : J \rightarrow J$$

Defined by

$$h_1 \rightarrow k_1 h_1 + k_2 = J, k_1, k_2 \in M$$

Also it is possible to connect those segments with the perpendicular segments. $Aut(Ef(1))$ orbits open the center $[Ef(1), Ef(1)]$ for any element $x \in [Ef(1), Ef(1)]$ and every neighborhood $Q(x, \gamma)$ of x have some element of $Ef(1)$ different then x .

$$Ef(1) - [Ef(1), Ef(1)] = Ef(1).$$

Theorem: 3

The affine control system Σ_c on the state space $Ef(1)$ is not have any equilibrium point and the associated bilinear system

$$\Sigma_c = (Ef(1), D_e)$$
 is control on the $Aut(Ef(1))$ orbit.

Proof:

For the control not having equilibrium point is necessary. Now consider the associated bilinear system

$$\Sigma_e = (Ef(1), D_e)$$
 is control on the $Aut(Ef(1))$ orbit.

$$\Phi_\delta : \partial L(G) \times L(G) \rightarrow \partial L(G) \times L(G)$$

$$\Phi_\delta = Id \times \frac{1}{\delta} \forall D + X \in cf(1) = \partial L(G) \times L(G), \text{ we have}$$

$$\Phi_\delta(D+X) = D + \frac{1}{\delta} X.$$

Since complete under the small permutations sufficiently large δ , $\Phi_\delta(\Sigma_c)$ is control on $S(1_e, 1) - [Ef(1), Ef(1)]$. Therefore, since normally control finite system are open on $S(1_e, 1)$. The system $\Phi_\delta(\Sigma_c)$ is also control on $B(1_e, 1) - [Ef(1), Ef(1)]$. Since the state space is connected, the affine system Σ_c is control on $Ef(1)$.

Lemma: 1

For the generalized Heisenberg lie group $H =: H(W, X, \alpha)$, the map $\varphi_\delta = \sqrt{\delta} Id \times \delta Id$, i.e., $\Phi_\delta(w, g) = (\sqrt{\delta} w, \delta g)$ is an automorphism.

Proof:

The mapping Φ_δ is 1-1 and onto its image.

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_\delta((w_1, g_1) * (w_2, g_2)) &= \Phi_\delta(w_1 + w_2, \\ &g_1 + g_2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha(w_1, w_2)) \\ &= (\sqrt{\delta} Id w_1 + \sqrt{\delta} Id w_2, \delta Id g_1 + \delta Id g_2 + \frac{\delta Id}{2} \alpha(w_1, w_2)) \end{aligned}$$

by bilinearity of α

$$\begin{aligned} &(\sqrt{\delta} Id w_1 + \sqrt{\delta} Id w_2, \delta Id g_1 + \delta Id g_2 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha(\sqrt{\delta} w_1, \sqrt{\delta} w_2)) \\ &= (\sqrt{\delta} Id w_1, \delta Id g_1) * (\sqrt{\delta} Id w_2, \delta Id g_2) \\ &= \Phi_\delta(w_1, g_1) * \Phi_\delta(w_2, g_2). \end{aligned}$$

This proves that Φ_δ is an automorphism.

Lemma: 2

Let H be a generalized Heisenberg Lie group. Then there exist a dense $Aut(H)$ -orbit.

Proof:

$$\text{The set } \varphi =: \exp(L(H) - [L(H), L(H)]) = H - [H, H]$$

is an $Aut(H)$ -orbit of H . The exponential map is a global diffeomorphism for simply connected nilpotent Lie groups. Two elements $X, Y \in \varphi$ the line segment mod XY parallel to $[H, H]$, can be connected via a line segment by taking once X as a initial point so that the function that connection $f_s : \varphi \rightarrow \varphi$ defined by $X \rightarrow k_1 X + k_2 = Y$, where $k_1, k_2 \in IM$, is an automorphism. Actually it is possible to connect these segments with the perpendicular segments to each oyer via the same way. That $Aut(H)$ -orbit of H is φ is open. In fact, if $\dim Z = 1$ the center $[H, H]$ forms a line for any Heisenberg group $[X, Y] = G$, $X, Y, G \in L(H)$. For the density, any $x \in [H, H]$ every ball $B(x, \gamma)$

$$B(x, \gamma) \cap H - [H, H] \neq \emptyset.$$

Thus, $H - [H, H] = H$.

Theorem: 4

Let G be a non-compact connected Lie group and $L(G)$ be its Lie algebra. Then, compact subsets of G are not G_Y -invariant, if the control system on G is an invariant system.

Proof:

For $\forall x \in G$, $\forall X \in L(G)$ and $\forall k \in IM$, the differentiable curve $\rho x(;x) : (c, e) \subset IM \rightarrow G$ is defined $\rho x(k, x) = X_k(x)$. Assume that $F \subset G$ is a compact and G_Y -invariant subset. Each vector field $X \in L(G)$ is complete. Consider any open covering

$$E = \{V_i \mid i \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}. \text{ Therefore, } \forall_i \gamma x(k, V_i) \text{ is an open}$$

covering of K , since $X_k(x)$, $\forall x \in K$. K is compact, therefore it can be covered by a finite subfamily of $A_\delta = \{\delta x(k, V_i) \mid i \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$. Then, inverse images of the elements of A_δ covers IM , which is a contradiction.

References

1. Helgason S, Differential Geometry, Lie Groups and Symmetric Spaces, Pure Appl. Math., 80, Academic Press, New York, 1978.
2. Sussmann H, Some properties of vector fields systems that are not altered by small perturbations, Journal of Differential Equations, 20 (1976), 292-315.
3. Buliga M, "Sub-Riemannian geometry and Lie groups. Part I", arXiv:math.MG/0210189, (2002).
4. Stroppel M, Homogeneous symplectic maps and almost homogeneous Heisenberg groups, Forum Math., 11 (1999), 659-672.
5. Nielsen O. A., "Unitary representations and coadjoint orbits of low - dimensional nilpotent Lie groups", Queen's Papers in Pure Appl. Math.e3 (1983).

